

Scenarios of Societal Security and Business Continuity Cycles

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Abstract : Societal security, continuity scenarios, and methodological cycling approach understands in this article. Namely, societal security organizational challenges ask implementation of international standards BS 25999-2 and global ISO 22300 which is a family of standards for business continuity management system. Efficient global organization system is distinguished of high entity's complexity, connectivity, and interoperability, having not only cooperative relations in a fact. Competing business have numerous participating 'enemies', which are in apparent or hidden opponent and antagonistic roles with prosperous organization systems, resulting to a crisis scene or even to a battle theater. Organization business continuity scenarios are necessary for such 'a play' preparedness, planning, management, and overmastering in real environments.

Keywords : business continuity, societal security, crisis scenarios cycles, interoperability

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